

A LIGHT FROM THE EAST **Life and Legacy of Aloysius Pieris SJ**

In Sri Lanka and India, in Asia and across the world Aloysius Pieris SJ (1934-2026) will be remembered for his life and writings, and for many of his insights— theological and spiritual, Asian and universal. While the Society of Jesus and the Church in Sri Lanka mourn his loss, theologians globally recall a scholar whose contributions made a significant impact on diverse sectors over five decades. His books such as *An Asian Theology of Liberation; Love Meets Wisdom: A Christian Experience of Buddhism; Fire and Water: Basic Issues in Asian Buddhism and Christianity; God's Reign for God's Poor: A Return to the Jesus Formula; Prophetic Humour in Buddhism and Christianity; Give Vatican II a Chance: Yes to Incessant Renewal, No to Reform of the Reforms* engaged the pundits and laity alike, inviting Christians, Buddhists, and others to take local contexts seriously in their efforts to work for the wellbeing of others. The subtitles of the books illustrate the interests that were close to his heart.

Aloysius Pieris was born at Ampitiya, Sri Lanka, and joined the Jesuits in 1953. Secular and religious studies took him to India, Italy, Germany, etc., and he was ordained a priest in 1965. The churning and the deliberations of the Second Vatican Council would have a lasting impact on him. In order to be rooted in the native soil, he learned Sanskrit and Pali (apart from Latin, Greek, and Hebrew) and got a doctorate in Buddhist philosophy. In the backdrop of the unrest of the 1970s, visibly noticed in the youth in Sri Lanka, in 1974 Pieris established Tulana Research Centre for Encounter and Dialogue at Kelaniya, Sri Lanka. Literally, Tulana means balance or scales (implies discernment) and it

provided a space for silence and prayer, reading and research, conversations and conversion.

Memorably, Aloysius Pieris described Asia (certainly it applies to most Asian countries) as the land of ‘many poor’ and ‘many religions.’ Also, he famously stated that a theologian here, to be credible and effective, is required to undergo ‘double baptism’: one ‘at the Jordon of Asian religion’ and, the other ‘at the Calvary of Asian poverty.’ Unlike the others who were developing liberation theologies in Latin America, Pieris insisted that theologians in Asia must understand and critically engage the religions (including their cultures and spiritualities) that have profound impact on people’s lives. He suggested that both ‘cosmic’ and ‘meta-cosmic’ aspects of Asian religions, which themselves contain liberative dimensions, need to be brought into the conversations.

In a way, Pieris is a quintessential Vatican II theologian. He observed it, understood it, interpreted it, and tried to apply its fruits to the Asian contexts. His thought provided a sharper socio-cultural analysis, indispensable to understand the causes of poverty in Asian scenarios. Similarly, while he acknowledged that religions require critique and cleansing, in them he found dialogue partners. In his view, western lenses are helpful but inadequate to study and understand theology in a complex world, and it needs to be nourished by the waters from the other rivers, be they Asian or African, classical or indigenous!

Visitors to Tulana centre will remember Pieris as a kind and caring host. In the presence of *Vagdevi* (Lady Knowledge) there, while people share meals and laughter, ideas cross-pollinate, leaving all enriched. Pieris’ life and legacy will continue to illuminate Asian and global theologies, ensuring that God’s reign brings freedom and joy to all. May *Agape* embrace *Dharma*, and, together, may they hold us all.

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